

Do student initial expectations about PBL match their final perceptions?

Sandra Fernandes^{1,2}, Anabela C. Alves³, Celina P. Leão³

¹ Portucalense Institute for Human Development, Portucalense University, Porto, Portugal;

² Research Centre on Child Studies – CIEC, University of Minho, Portugal

³ ALGORITMI Centre, Department of Production and Systems, School of Engineering, University of Minho, Guimarães, Portugal

Email: sandraf@upt.pt; anabela@dps.uminho.pt; cpl@dps.uminho.pt

Abstract

This paper presents findings from a PBL approach which takes place in the Integrated Master's degree of Industrial Engineering and Management (IEM), at the University of Minho, Portugal. It is part of a curricular unit in the 1st year of the 1st semester called Integrated Project of Industrial Engineering and Management 1 (IPIEM1). This curricular unit follows PBL approach. In total, 56 students participated in the PBL approach in the academic year 2019/2020, forming six teams of nine to ten students. This paper aims to analyse students' initial expectations about PBL and compare them with their final perceptions concerning their experience. Data were collected from an online survey, applied at the beginning of the project (n=41), in the 1st week, and at the end of the project (n=33), in the last week. This survey has been used successfully, since the year 2008/2009, to evaluate PBL approaches from students' point of view. In 2019/2020, the survey was adapted to be used for the first time, also at the start of the project, to collect students' initial expectations. Authors understand that the first week of the project is very intense and demanding, as students become aware of the several challenges which they will face throughout the semester. Findings from the comparative analysis of the survey show that teamwork appears as one of the most positive aspects about the PBL experience, but also one of the most challenging issues for students to overcome. Beyond the "normal" students' concerns about teamwork, high workload, and other issues, the second survey revealed interesting insights from students in regard to their understanding of the PBL assessment model, that were not perceived in the first week. Qualitative data from findings will also be explored and discussed in the paper.

Keywords: Industrial Engineering and Management Education; first-year students, student perceptions; project-based learning (PBL).

1 Introduction

Project-based learning (PBL) is an active learning approach where a team of students works together through a period of time to solve large-scale complex open-ended problems (Powell & Weenk, 2003). This author, who designated this approach as Project-led Education (PLE), with its origins in the Engineering Education field in Denmark, describes this methodology as the following: "a team of students tackles the project, provides a solution and delivers by an agreed time (a deadline) a team product such as a prototype and a team report. Students show what they have learned by discussing with staff the team product and reflecting on how they achieved it" (Powell, 2004, p. 221). At the School of Engineering at the University of Minho, PBL has been used in several engineering programmes (Industrial Engineering and Management; Mechanical Engineering; Electrical Engineering; Polymer Engineering; Textile Engineering) as a positive strategy to promote active learning and increase student motivation for learning.

According to Powell (1999), it is important to present a balanced picture of PBL by recognising its advantages and disadvantages. Below, we will present findings about the effectiveness of PBL and the positive and less positive aspects that are related to its implementation. The identification of these characteristics of PBL are important to guide the discussion of this paper, which aims to analyse students' expectations and compare them with their final perceptions about PBL.

Powell (1999, p. 13) identifies a list of advantages of PBL, namely: 1) Students are strongly motivated to work hard and effectively (on projects); 2) Students learn to learn; 3) Students pass rates can improve; 4) There is better communication and teamwork by students; 5) Students build up a learning partnership with each other and (in later years) with staff: learning together; 6) The syllabus is seen in the context of the project; 7) Students

find out what they don't know and can seek what they need; 8) Students learn to work to agreed deadlines; 9) PBL identifies early on those students who are "suitable" for real engineering at academic level; 10) Reasonable group expectations by staff and students put psychological pressure on all students to succeed. Unsuitable and lazy students are thrown out; 11) There are still opportunities for some traditional examinations where depth of understanding in specific subjects can be explored in detail; 12) Teachers must talk to each other about education issues across boundaries, 13) Staff must work together in project planning.

Apparent disadvantages of project-led education, according to Powell (1999, p. 15), include the following: 1) Students do not have precise knowledge of all the most advanced theories; 2) Students do not have a lot of memory knowledge; 3) The atmosphere compels students to work at the group tempo; 4) PBL is frustrating for those students who find it difficult to work in groups; 5) Not all the syllabus can be covered by any project; 6) It is not always easy to motivate students on subjects such as Maths; 7) Assessment is certainly not easy; 8) Project rooms cost money; 9) Tutors need to be open-minded and supportive of student development; 10) Tutor support of groups is a new skill and needs training; 11) There are big challenges for staff when students bring in good but unexpected questions; 12) In later years of the course, tutors cannot always "know everything", thus we need teams of tutors and recognition of the need to do some redirecting of student questions to other tutors; 13) PBL requires teamwork for tutors, teachers, administrators and integration over the traditional subject boundaries.

Taking in consideration these important remarks about PBL and their implications on students' and teachers' role, this paper analysis students' perceptions about a PBL semester, comparing their initial expectations (after the first week of the project) with their final perceptions (last week of the project), in the first year of an engineering degree programme at the University of Minho, Portugal. The aim of this study is to compare the results before and after the PBL semester, based on the application of an online questionnaire, including both quantitative and qualitative data. After a brief introduction to the definition of PBL and its principles, in the Introduction of this paper, section two describes the context of the study, followed by the research methods in section three. The results are presented and discussed on section four, which is organized based on the quantitative and qualitative data. The last section of the paper presents the conclusions and final remarks.

2 Study context

This section briefly presents the study context by introducing the Industrial Engineering and Management program of the first year, first semester project-based learning (PBL) (IEM11_PBL) developed in the context of the course called "Integrated Project of Industrial Engineering and Management 1" (IPIEM1). An overview of the IEM11_PBL is given, followed by a short description of the first and final week moments, which correspond to moments of high workload for both teacher and students (Alves et al., 2019) and also to the moment when the survey discussed in this paper was applied.

2.1 Description of IEM11_PBL

The first semester of the first year of Industrial Engineering and Management includes six courses and currently such courses are all integrated in PBL. This was not always the case but since the first experience that occurred in the academic year of 2004_2005 (Alves et al., 2007; Lima et al., 2007), it was permanently an endeavour. This was accomplished after some years with a more or less stable team of teachers collaboration that manage the difficulties of this complex educational project (Alves et al., 2016a; Alves et al., 2016b).

Its complexity comes from various factors. One of these factors is the dimension of staff coordination team that includes all teachers from the courses involved, that are from different departments belonging to different schools, tutors and educational researches. The number of European credits is five, equal for each course, in the European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS), as the Figure shows. Introduction to IEM (IEM), IPIEM1 and Algorithms and programming (AP) are from School of Engineering (brick colour), department of Production and Systems (the first two) and Information system (third one). General Chemistry (GC), Linear Algebra (LA) and Calculus (CC) are from School of Sciences (blue colour), department of Chemistry (the first one) and Mathematics department (the last two courses).

Figure 1. Courses of IEM11_PBL

Some or part of the contents of each course must be included in the project developed in the IPIEM1, according to each teachers guidelines and teaching styles, i.e. by specific task assignments. Students do these tasks in teams, the teacher provides feedback and students show their learning in the presentations, reports and project development. Each course has its own assessment method that could include various components such as tasks grade, written tests, among others. Students, normally, have more than one assessment moment by week of each course and IPIEM1. The main idea is that they work continuously for the project integrating along the semester (from September to February) components of each course in the project (Alves et al., 2019). The following section explains how IPIEM1 is planned.

2.2 Planning and development of IPIEM1

This section details the planning and development of IPIEM1. First of all, it is important to notice that this educational project is managed as a real project where the resources, time and cost are intended to be levelled, being divided in five main phases with the respective durations: 1) preparation (3 months); 2) set-up (1 month); 3) start-up (1 week); 4) execution (6 months); 5) conclusion (1 week) (Alves et al., 2009; Lima et al., 2012). The first two phases just involve staff coordination team. By doing this, students have also an example of how to manage a project, one of the competencies to acquire in IPIEM1. So, the first step is to plan the project and deliver a document, the learning project guide (Equipa de coordenação 2019_20, 2019) to the students with the description of project, i.e., it is similar to a project specification or project charter. This document has 14 pages and includes the following sections for the academic year 2019_20: 1) Introduction; 2) Advantages and challenges of the process; 3) Students; 4) Staff coordination team; 5) Tutor role; 6) Project description (theme, brief description, objectives); 7) Competencies (technical and transversal); 8) Timing (schedule, semester plan, milestones and first week project-pilot organization); 9) Assessment (for IPIEM1 and courses); 10) Physical resources; 11) E-learning platform and 12) Commitment declaration and checklist of space and material requirement. This document is delivered to students in the first presentation from the staff coordinator of semester where the project is presented to the students, which occurs in the start-up phase. After that, students are in conditions to start to develop the project. Each section of the document is a rich part of discussion but for this paper just the activities performed in the first and final week will be deeply discussed in the following sections. Before that, it is important to present, at least, the milestones where teams have some deliverables to send to the staff coordination team and the assessment model. The list, schedule and main deliverables of the milestones are presented in the Table .

Table 1. Milestones and deliverables of academic year 2019_20

Phase	#	Week	Deliverable
Execution	M1	Week 2	14h10 – 17h00: Mini-project presentation (10' min/team + 5' discussion).
	M2	Week 6	14h10 – 17h00: Intermediate presentation (10' min/team + 5' discussion).
	M3	Week 9	14h10 – 17h00: Extended tutorial (20' min/team).
	M4	Week 12	18h00 – Deliverable: Preliminary report (maximum of 50 pages).
	M5	Week 16	18h00 – Deliverable: Final Report (maximum of 60 pages) + Prototypes.
Part of Conclusion	M6	Week 18	9h30 – 11h30: Individual written test about the project (2 questions). 9h10 – 13h00: Final presentation & discussion (15' min/team + 20' discussion).

The deliverable of M1 and M3 are usually not assessed, all the others are assessed by course teachers. The assessment model and its components (individual and team) are presented in the Figure 2.

Figure 2. Assessment model of IPIEM1 of academic year 2019_20

2.2.1 First week of the project

The first week represents a high workload for teachers, in particular, for the coordinator, and students. It is a stressful moment but it is also a discovery moment for the students, meeting a new university, new colleagues, and for some, even a new city and country (international students). The students have to process a lot of information given in the first week of classes. During this week, students will have the welcome presentations from the Rector, from the dean of the department, from the course director and finally, from the coordinator of the semester and of the IPIEM1.

In a session organized by staff coordination team, the coordinator presents, through videos and reports from UNESCO, the global changes needing different competencies for the 21st century to contextualize the importance PBL. Then, introduces the IPIEM1, the historical of PBL editions in IEM11_PBL, some alumni testifies in person or written about PBL importance, the staff coordination team, the learning project guide, the tutor role, the milestones, the project theme of this particular year, the assessment model, the project-pilot, the semester plan and schedule, the e-learning tools and finally, the teams formed by one member of staff coordination team before this presentation and the tutors assigned to them. After this, they go with the coordinator and tutors to the projects rooms for them to start working if they want, or at least, to know each other and organize the first assignment as a team. Because there are only six spaces for the teams (two project rooms) only six teams are formed, that will put nine to ten members by team (always dependent on the number of freshman students). Also, IEM is always a programme with many working students (older) and transferred students that are also grouped in teams but do not take part in the PBL project (Alves et al., 2018).

The first-week project-pilot organization is also described in the learning guide project, section 8, and the idea is to pass by all phases of the project in a short period of time. A document of one page is provided to the teams with the description of the pilot project explaining what is expected from the teams, the duration of the activity, how they prepare and when to present and which main points to focus, reflecting also in the learning lessons to retrieve. Mainly, it consists in a week or a little more to prepare a presentation doing a state-of-art of the theme chosen for the specific year. In the academic year 2019_20, the theme was to design a production system to process/valorise organic residues into a valuable product, using composting or other process. An example of a first presentation of a team is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. First presentation of a team

The teams must also have to set-up a blog where the team introduces itself and their project. The blog must be updated with diary meetings and tasks that they are doing, the data and information being collected. The objective is to monitor team work. This blog was one of the student assessment components, for the first time this year.

2.2.2 Final week of the project

The final week also represents a lot of work because it is the conclusion of almost six long months of hard work including activities, tasks, tests, training sessions, events, and, of course, “praxe” (activities organized by the third grade students to welcome the freshman). The main deliverables in the last week are the final presentation and discussion done in teams and the individual written test about the project, synthetized in the final report, delivered in two weeks before.

With the final presentation, teams also present videos of production system in Legos Mindstorm demonstration and of the product, physical prototypes of the product, holder names in tags, some flyers of their product/company, among others elements that are optional elements (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Last presentation of the teams: elements bring by them to the presentation

After this last presentation, teams must deliver the project rooms keys. Before that, they must assure everything is clean and took all of their belongings. This does not have been an easy task, so in this academic year they were forced to sign a commitment declaration (section 12 in the learning project guide) where they declare to do this last task before leaving.

The last presentation means the last item for obtaining the grade. After that, the teams will be waiting for the final grades. Meanwhile, they are asked to fill out the questionnaire referred in the following section 3. But one more task is asked of them, the one in participating voluntarily in the final workshop organized by the staff coordination team in order to discuss the semester functioning. What ran well, what did not run well and suggestions for the future. In 2019_20 academic year, the coordinator started the workshop by presenting the summary of all projects, using padlet where all team elements were registered, and a video with all important moments occurred during the workshop. After that, the workshop was organized in four main parts: suggestions given by the students from the previous year and how these were implemented/not implemented and why, open discussion in focus groups about the main dimensions of the PBL questionnaire (as will be presented in the next section), the grades discussion and the questionnaire results. From this workshop, a lot of suggestions are obtained, being collected and used to improve the IEM11_PBL (Alves et al., 2012; Alves et al., 2019; Fernandes et al., 2014; Mesquita et al., 2009). Examples include having only one tutor third year student by team (Alves et al., 2017) and reducing the number of tasks and milestones (Alves et al., 2009; Alves et al., 2019).

3 Methodology

To analyse students perceptions about the PBL semester, data were collected from an online survey, applied at the beginning of the project (n=41), in the 1st week, and at the end of the project (n=33), in the last week. The survey is organized in six sections, including the following topics: i) project theme (D1); ii) learning and competences developed (D2); iii) teamwork (D3); iv) teacher’s role (D4); v) assessment model (D5); vi) PBL as a learning approach (D6), evaluated based on a 5-point agreement Likert scale (1 – strongly disagree to 5 – strongly agree). The online questionnaire also includes a set of open-ended questions for a better identification of the most positive (strengths) and less positive (weakness) aspects and suggestions for improvements. So, for the analysis, both quantitative and qualitative data will be considered. Due to the relevance of the topic, in this paper, the dimension that will be quantitatively analyzed is solely regarding the assessment model (v).

This survey has been used successfully, since the year 2008/2009, to evaluate PBL approaches from students’ point of view (e.g. A.C. Alves, Moreira, Fernandes, Leão, & Sousa, 2017; Mesquita et al., 2009). In 2019/2020, the survey was adapted to be used, for the first time, also at the start of the project, to collect students’ expectations of PBL. Authors understand that the first week of the project is very intense and demanding, as students become aware of the several challenges which they will face throughout the semester. The last week, where all developed activities and tasks in the project have been fulfilled and finished, allowing students a complete and comprehensive perception of how the semester run. These two moments will allow to understand and evaluate students’ perceptions change.

4 Results

This section is divided in two subsections according to the nature of the data in analysis: (1) qualitative data, from the open-ended questions of the questionnaire, which provided an overall perspective of the dimensions most and least positively evaluated by students, as well as suggestions for future improvement; and, 2) quantitative data, based on results from the closed questions using a 5-Likert scale, which are analyzed solely in regard to the “assessment model” dimension (D5) from the questionnaire. The comparative analysis is described based on the results obtained in two different moments: first week and last week of the PBL semester.

4.1 Overall results from the PBL questionnaire – first and last week

Based on a thematic content analysis (Bardin, 2011), qualitative data from the open-ended questions was organized in categories. The frequency of the topic was also included to show the relevance of each category mentioned by students. Table2 presents a summary of the main results achieved.

Table 2. Comparison of qualitative results, before and after the PBL experience

Dimensions	Initial Survey - first week (n _b = 41)	Final Survey - last week (n _a = 33)
Most positive aspects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teamwork (26) • Project theme (9) • Successful integration at university (2) • Sharing ideas (2) • Presence of all teachers at the Mini-project presentation (1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of transversal skills (14) • Teamwork (9) • Understanding of the curricular units (7) • Successful integration at university (4) • Contact with future professional area (2)
Less positive aspects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teamwork (7) • Problems with time management (6) • Mini-project presentation (5) • Feeling lost in the first week (4) • Greater support from teachers (1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workload and tasks (14) • Teamwork (5) • Stress (5) • Assessment methods (5) • Nothing to refer (3) • Others (3)
Suggestions for improvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review project presentation dates (3) • Better link between project theme and the curricular units (3) • Improve group meetings and organization (3) • Develop more research (1) • Provide lecture about the project theme (1) • More information about the project goals (1) • More presence of teachers in project rooms (1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review assessment process and methods (21) • More active role by teachers (6) • Review task deadlines and milestones (6) • Improve the project rooms’ conditions (3) • Nothing to refer (2) • Improve the team formation process (1) • Select attractive themes for the project (1)

In general, it is possible to say that students' expectations about PBL in the first week match their final perceptions about the experience. One of the most positive aspects mentioned by students about this experience is definitely teamwork, both at the start (f=26) and also at the end (f=9) of the project. Teamwork has a strong influence on students' work and performance, either in a positive or negative way. These quotes from students' answers, after the first week of the project, confirm the importance of teamwork for students:

- *The sense of feeling that my team can jointly develop something useful considering the qualities of each one.*
- *The work developed with my team throughout the week.*
- *The friendly relationship with team members.*
- *Learn to deal with different personalities and get the best out of each one.*

Also, at the end of the project, students emphasised the importance of teamwork and its role for the project success:

- *During the project, it was difficult, sometimes, to learn to deal with the different opinions of my colleagues, in addition, the pressure to deliver everything on time and to know that it was not just up to me was not easy. I think they are many people on each team and that sometimes becomes difficult to manage.*
- *From the moment that the project was presented to us, there was a strong union between the PBL group members. So, not only did it facilitate our integration at the university, but it also made the work that we knew we had to do more interesting from the start. PBL gave us the possibility to carry out a project from its initial phase to its final phase, so we were able to acquire knowledge that will help us in the future life. In addition, although it can be quite arduous and stressful, it allows us to constantly overcome ourselves, developing many transversal skills.*

As mentioned in this last quote, PBL has a positive impact for the successful integration of 1st year students at the university, which is a great advantage of PBL considering that the transition to higher education is always a difficult and challenging phase of students' life (Araújo, 2017; Casanova, Araújo, & Almeida, 2020).

Concerning the suggestions for improvement, the majority of students (f=21) agree that the assessment method in PBL needs to be reviewed. This is definitely the main suggestion presented by students, who identify problems related to the peer assessment method, the final test of the project and the individual classifications, as issues that require further improvement in the assessment process of PBL.

- *The individual test does not fulfil its purpose! I propose that this test is completely reformulated, because even the members involved in the execution of tasks like WBS did not memorize it. Since the test is so short when compared to the execution of the entire project, in addition to being reformulated, it should have a lower weight in the final classification. Note that the classification obtained in this test was the main differentiator of the final grades of the group! "*
- *The final test does not correctly assess the role of each person in the project and whether or not they were aware of it. Peer assessment is necessary, but it should not count so much because many times our colleagues are unaware of the work underlying the results obtained.*

These qualitative results are in agreement with the quantitative results and express and explain the directions of students' opinions.

The problems concerning the assessment model of PBL are a recurring topic on the evaluation of PBL editions. It is considered the most controversial issue of PBL, both by students and the staff coordination team. The research team at the University of Minho has developed several studies and research projects to better understand this phenomena and develop a continuous improvement process (Alves et al., 2017; Alves et al., 2016a, 2016b; Fernandes et al., 2009, 2012a, 2012b; Lima et al., 2017).

4.2 Results related to the "Assessment Model" dimension

The assessment model dimension considered (D5) 10 items as described in Table 2. For the comparative analysis, the difference between students' mean rates considered was (before – after), assuming that, in average, the results for the assessment PBL project dimension is reduced. In Table 2 also some descriptive statistics (mean (m), standard deviation (sd), median (M), minimum (min), maximum (max)) for all the items considered for the assessment dimension are presented. A total of 41 (=n_b) students answered the online questionnaire in the first week and 33 (=n_a) in the last week. For the data analysis the SPSS statistical tool was used and non-parametric Mann-Whitney test U was considered (as alternative to the t-test for two independent

samples), through Z-score value, to analyze differences between students' perceptions by moment, with a significance level of 5%.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics and difference between students' mean rates (before – after = b – a) for D5.

Dimension	Item	m, sd, M, min, max		Statistics Z-score
		b	a	(b – a)
v. Assessment model	D5.1 I have read and understood the assessment criteria in the Student Guide.	4.2, .74, 4, 3, 5	4.1, .74, 4, 2, 5	.231, p=.817
	D5.2 The number of milestones during the project should be lower.	4.1, .63, 4, 3, 5	2.9, .76, 3, 1, 5	5.884, p=.000^a
	D5.3 Teacher's feedback on reports and presentations was clear.	4.7, .47, 5, 4, 5	3.5, .87, 4, 1, 5	5.989, p=.000^a
	D5.4 Peer evaluation is an appropriate tool for evaluating teamwork.	4.2, .64, 4, 3, 5	3.4, 1.22, 4, 1, 5	3.003, p=.003^a
	D5.5 The results of the peer evaluation reflect the commitment of each element.	4.3, .59, 4, 3, 5	3.1, 1.26, 3, 1, 5	4.280, p=.000^a
	D5.6 Evaluating another team's report was a useful experience for me and allowed me to learn.	4.3, .60, 4, 3, 5	3.8, .83, 4, 1, 5	2.971, p=.003^a
	D5.7 The final individual test on the project helped me prepare for the final presentation.	4.1, .69, 4, 3, 5	2.1, 1.05, 2, 1, 5	5.410, p=.000^a
	D5.8 The project grade should be the same for all members of the group.	3.1, .98, 3, 1, 5	2.0, .77, 2, 1, 5	4.779, p=.000^a
	D5.9 I think that the weight of the individual test should be lower in the final individual assessment of the student.	3.3, .96, 3, 1, 5	4.0, 1.03, 4, 2, 5	-2.894, p=.004^a
	D5.10 In general, I am satisfied with the results obtained at the project.	4.3, .64, 4, 3, 5	3.5, 1.21, 4, 1, 5	3.178, p=.001^a

^a Statistically significant

With a single exception (D5.1 I have read an understood the assessment criteria), all students in average have change significantly their opinion during the moments beginning and end of the semester. The values reflect a changing to a more negative opinion regarding the several items in evaluation, showing that in average the initial expectations about PBL were higher than their final perceptions. This trend was particularly steep for D5.7 (The final individual test on the project helped me prepare for the final presentation), D5.3 (Teacher's feedback on reports and presentations was clear) and D5.2 (The number of milestones during the project should be lower). Namely the two last items, D5.3 and D5.2 show, somehow, a dissatisfaction regarding the teachers' feedback and strengthen the importance that the milestones have for the development of the PBL Project, despite the work involved.

However, results show that not everything has been negative or in a negative direction: item D5.9 increased, showing that, in average, students perceived that the weight of the individual test should be lower in the final individual assessment of the student. This issue is recurrent, however, it is teachers believe that this must be a term to be considered in the assessment model. The weight of the individual test on the student's final assessment has been undergoing significant changes over the past years (Anabela Alves et al., 2016a; Sandra Fernandes, Flores, & Lima, 2012).

5 Final remarks

This paper compares the initial expectations of IEM11_PBL students in the first and final week of the PBL phases that are the most intensive hard-working weeks. Although previous research and a number of studies have been developed about this PBL process, it was the first time that the survey was applied in two different moments. Beyond the "normal" and usual concerns about teamwork, high workload, time management and others issues identified by students, which were not, somehow, surprising, the second survey revealed

interesting insights about the assessment model, that were not at all perceived by students in the first week. Besides the continuous effort taken every year, by teachers and specially the PBL coordinator, to make students aware of how the PBL semester will impact on their final assessment and learning, this dimension seems to be something that is not entirely clear for students at the start of the semester. At the end of the semester, students certainly take many “lessons learned” from their PBL experience, which helps them to prepare themselves for the second semester in a more conscious and critical way. Based on the findings from our study, it is possible to recognize the major advantages of PBL, as stated in the introduction section of this study, which somehow relief the teachers and PBL coordinator in regard to the aspects that were considered less positive by students. These features are part of students’ learning process and should be seen as an opportunity for their own development. Future work should focus on supporting and improving PBL, following some of the valuable suggestions provided by students in the final survey.

Acknowledgments

This work has been supported by FCT – Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia within the R&D Units Project Scope: UIDB/00319/2020.

6 References

- Alves, A. C., Moreira, F., Sousa, R., & Lima, R. M. (2009). Teachers’ workload in a project-led engineering education approach. *International Symposium on Innovation and Assessment of Engineering Curricula*, 14. Valladolid.
- Alves, A.C., Moreira, F., Fernandes, S., Leão, C. P., & Sousa, R. (2017). PBL in the first year of an industrial engineering and management program: A journey of continuous improvement. *International Symposium on Project Approaches in Engineering Education*, 9.
- Alves, A.C., Moreira, F., Leão, C. P., Pereira, A. C., Pereira-Lima, S. M. M. A., Malheiro, M. T., ... Oliveira, S. (2019). Industrial engineering and management PBL implementation: An effortless experience? *International Symposium on Project Approaches in Engineering Education*, 9, 117–127.
- Alves, AC, Moreira, F., & Sousa, R. (2007). O papel dos tutores na aprendizagem baseada em projectos: três anos de experiência na Escola de Engenharia da Universidade do Minho. *Libro de Actas Do Congreso Internacional Galego-Portugués de Psicopedagogía. A.Coruña/Universidade Da Coruña: Revista Galego-Portuguesa de Psicología e Educación.*, (1), 1759–1770.
- Alves, Anabela C., Moreira, F., & Leão, C. P. (2018). Dealing With Student Profile Diversity in an Industrial Engineering and Management Program: PBL vs “Non-PBL.” *Volume 5: Engineering Education*, V005T07A007. <https://doi.org/10.1115/IMECE2018-86368>
- Alves, Anabela C., Moreira, F., Leão, C. P., & Teixeira, S. (2017). Tutoring Experiences in PBL of Industrial Engineering and Management Program: Teachers vs Students. *Volume 5: Education and Globalization*, 5, V005T06A008. <https://doi.org/10.1115/IMECE2017-71306>
- Alves, Anabela C., Sousa, R. M., Fernandes, S., Cardoso, E., Carvalho, M. A., Figueiredo, J., & Pereira, R. M. S. (2016a). Teacher’s experiences in PBL: implications for practice. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 41(2), 123–141. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043797.2015.1023782>
- Alves, Anabela C, Moreira, F., Mesquita, D., & Fernandes, S. (2012). Project-Based Learning in First Year, First Semester of Industrial Engineering and Management: Some Results. *Proceedings of the ASME 2012 International Mechanical Engineering Congress & Exposition IMECE2012*, 1–10.
- Alves, Anabela Carvalho, Moreira, F., Carvalho, M. A., Oliveira, S., Malheiro, M. T., Brito, I., ... Teixeira, S. (2019). Integrating Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics contents through PBL in an Industrial Engineering and Management first year program. *Production*, 29(x), 0–0. <https://doi.org/10.1590/0103-6513.20180111>
- Alves, Anabela, Sousa, R., Moreira, F., Carvalho, M. A., Cardoso, E., Pimenta, P., ... Mesquita, D. (2016b). Managing PBL difficulties in an industrial engineering and management program. *Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management*, 9(3), 586. <https://doi.org/10.3926/jiem.1816>
- Araújo, A. M. (2017). Sucesso no Ensino Superior: Uma revisão e conceptualização || Success in Higher Education: A review and conceptualization. *Revista de Estudios e Investigación En Psicología y Educación*. <https://doi.org/10.17979/reipe.2017.4.2.3207>
- Bardin, L. (2011). Análise do Conteúdo. In *Edições 70*.
- Casanova, J. R., Araújo, A. M., & Almeida, L. S. (2020). Dificuldades na adaptação académica dos estudantes do 1º ano do Ensino Superior. *Revista E-Psi*, 9(1), 165–181.
- Equipa de coordenação 2019_20. (2019). *Guia do projeto aprendizagem no contexto Project-Based Learning (PBL): Projeto*

Integrado de Engenharia e Gestão Industrial 1 (PIEGI1_MIEGI11).

- Fernandes, S., Flores, M. A., & Lima, R. M. (2012a). Student assessment in project based learning. In *Springer* (Vol. 9789460919, pp. 147–159). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-6091-958-9_10
- Fernandes, S., Flores, M. A., & Lima, R. M. (2012b). Students' views of assessment in project-led engineering education: Findings from a case study in Portugal. *Assessment and Evaluation in Higher Education*, 37(2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2010.515015>
- Fernandes, S., Mesquita, D., & Lima, R. et al. (2009). The impact of peer assessment on teamwork and student evaluation. *Innovation and Assessment of Engineering Curricula*, 125–136.
- Fernandes, Sandra, Flores, M. A., & Lima, R. M. (2012). Students' views of assessment in project-led engineering education: Findings from a case study in Portugal. *Assessment and Evaluation in Higher Education*, 37(2), 163–178. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2010.515015>
- Fernandes, Sandra, Mesquita, D., Flores, M. A., & Lima, R. M. (2014). Engaging students in learning: Findings from a study of project-led education. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 39(1), 55–67. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043797.2013.833170>
- Lima, R.M., Carvalho, D., Sousa, R. M., Alves, A., Moreira, F., Mesquita, D., & Fernandes, S. (2012). A project management framework for planning and executing interdisciplinary learning projects in engineering education. In *Project Approaches to Learning in Engineering Education: The Practice of Teamwork*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-6091-958-9_5
- Lima, R.M., Dinis-Carvalho, J., Sousa, R. M., Alves, A. C., Moreira, F., Fernandes, S., & Mesquita, D. (2017). Ten years of project-based learning (PBL) in industrial engineering and management at the University of Minho. In *PBL in Engineering Education: International Perspectives on Curriculum Change*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-6300-905-8>
- Lima, Rui M, Carvalho, D., Flores, A., & Van Hattum-Janssen, N. (2007). A case study on project led education in engineering: students and teachers perceptions. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 32(3), 337–347. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043790701278599>
- Mesquita, D., Alves, A., Fernandes, S., Moreira, F., & Lima, R. M. (2009). A First Year and First Semester Project-Led Engineering Education Approach 2 Organization Model. In D. Carvalho, N. van Hattum, & R. M. Lima (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 1st Ibero- American symposium on project approaches in engineering education (PAEE'2009)* (pp. 181–189). Braga, Portugal: Centro de Investigação em Educação, Universidade do Minho.
- Powell, P. (1999). From classical to project-led education. In António Sérgio pouzada (Ed.), *Project Based Learning. Project-led Education and Group Learning*. (pp. 11–42). Braga: Thematic Network Plastics in Engineering.
- Powell, P. C. (2004). Assessment of team-based projects in project-led education. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 29(2), 221–230. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043790310001633205>
- Powell, P., & Weenk, W. (2003). *Project-Led Engineering Education* (Vol. 53). <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107415324.004>